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THE NOTION OF LINGUISTIC PERSONALITY IN TRANSLATION STUDIES

Annation: the given article below discusses different viewpoints on anthropocentric paradigm – Linguistic personality, which is one of the modern terms in translation studies.

Key words: *linguistic personality, translator's personality, anthropocentric paradigm, human mental activity, communicative behavior, culture and society.*

Аннотация: в данной статье рассматриваются различные точки зрения на антропоцентрическую парадигму – языковую личность, которая является одним из современных терминов в переводоведении.

Ключевые слова: *языковая личность, личность переводчика, антропоцентрическая парадигма, психическая деятельность человека, коммуникативное поведение, культура и общество.*

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola antropotsentrik paradigma – tarjimashunoslikdagi zamonaviy atamalardan biri bo'lgan lingvistik shaxs haqidagi turli nuqtayi nazarlarni ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *lingvistik shaxs, tarjimonning shaxsiyati, antropotsentrik paradigma, insonning aqliy faoliyati, kommunikativ xatti-harakatlar, madaniyat va jamiyat.*

At the end of the 20th century language and the following anthropocentric paradigm – “linguistic personality” was studied from the perspective of native speakers. Issues related to the feelings of a person forced to live within the constraints of a particular language were investigated, and the processes of human mental activity reflected in language were analyzed. The concept of a linguistic personality has become increasingly popular. The reality around a person is transformed through thinking into a system of images that form a picture of the world. The anthropocentric nature of the worldview is expressed in its focus on humans. According to V.N. Telia, the anthropocentric canon, a “naive picture of the world” is created that finds expression in the very possibility of thinking about natural phenomena or abstract concepts as objectified constants. The linguistic picture of the world is based on the anthropocentric principle, which states that man is the measure of all things”. It should be noted that the ideas that led to the concept of the “linguistic picture of the world” in the late 20th century were present long before their formulation. V. von Humboldt, one of the first linguists and philosophers, suggested that language reflects the worldview of its speakers: “different languages are the organs of the original thinking and perception of nations”.

These ideas were further developed by Leo Weisgerber in his research. He introduced the concept of a linguistic picture to the scientific terminology. The linguistic picture of the world is, on the one hand, a result of the historical development of an ethnos and its language, and on the other hand, it shapes the path of its further development. The linguistic picture can be seen as a living organism with a complex structure that includes multiple levels. Linguistic expression is a special set of sounds, sound combinations, and features of the articulatory apparatus in native speakers. It includes

prosodic characteristics, vocabulary, word formation capabilities, syntax, and phrase and sentence structure. Additionally, it includes the paremiological baggage of the language.

The linguistic picture of the world shapes the overall communicative behavior, understanding of nature and man's inner world, and the language system. Thinking and the native language are used to perceive the world. L. Weisgerber believed that the way we reflect reality is idiosyncratic and corresponds to the static form of the language. To what extent a person speaks the language determines how well they know the world. The world is also discussed in the works of American linguists, Edward Sapir and Benjamin Whorf, who created the unique theory of linguistic relativity. They argue that a person navigates the world without the help of language, and that language is just a tool to solve specific problems of communication and thinking. Sapir writes that the idea that language is an essential part of our perception of the world is an illusion. Indeed, he argues that the world is largely built on the linguistic habits and conventions of a particular social group. Moreover, V.A. Maslova believes that the linguistic picture of the world is a common cultural heritage of the nation, which is structured and multilevel. This linguistic picture of the world determines communicative behavior and understanding of the external and internal world of a person, reflecting the way of speech-thinking activity that is characteristic of a particular era with its spiritual, cultural, and national values.

Indeed, the words about human communicative behavior in this statement by V.A. Maslova are important, as the linguistic picture of the world largely determines communication in one society or another. The concept of linguistic personality in anthropological linguistics is extremely significant, as this concept is the tool that creates language varieties. If the question

